

“NOTE ON THE LAND SNAILS OF BUÇACO FOREST (CENTRAL PORTUGAL)”

João Fidalgo * e Pedro Callapez **

1. Introduction: Buçaco Forest, situated on the NV Buçaco Ridge, is an interesting arboretum with many introduced vegetable species, mainly woody, which are almost perfectly adapted.

It is localized between the altitude of 250 and 547 m (on a place called “Cruz Alta”), and is completely surrounded by a wall of 3 m height and almost 6 Km perimeter, covering about 400 ha of woodland.

The climate is moderate and humid. The minimal temperatures almost never fall to 0° C and the absolute maximum is 39° C (Allorge, 1974).

The precipitation is about 1400-1500 mm per year and the snow fall is weak and uncommon. Fog, however, is dense and appears frequently during summer and autumn, persisting until 10-11 a.m. or even later elevated places. The water richness is tested by the number of springs, lakes and streams.

Showing the wet climate, there are in the wood 60 species of hepaticas and 142 different mosses (ALLORGE, 1974). Fungus and ferns are also very common as patent in the local toponimic — “the Ferns Valley”. There is a big number of exotic species, mainly gimnospermics, but it is interesting to note the existence of an autochthonal residual forest, of climax type, with *Ilex* s.p., *Viburnum* s.p. *Quercus* s.p. and others. However, when concerning all the woodland, the genus *Cupressus*, *Cedrus*, *Pinus* and *Quercus* are dominant.

Additionally, there is an abundant shrubby stratum, yet subject to occasional pruning by the National Forestry Services.

All these vegetal coverture furnish a thick leaf-mould which appears to have optimal conditions to sustent an important biotic community, including land snails.

2. List of species: During our dislocations to Buçaco we collected some samples inside the wood, including samples for sieving, which gave the following list of 21 species:

fam. *Ellobiidae*

Carychium ibazoricum Bank & Gittenberger, 1985

* Chamusca da Beira, 3400 OLIVEIRA DO HOSPITAL.

** Museu e Laboratório Mineralógico e Geológico da Universidade de Coimbra, 3049 COIMBRA CODEX.

fam. Cochlicopidae
Cochlicopa lubrica (Müller, 1774)

fam. Vertiginidae
Columella aspera Waldén, 1966

fam. Pupillidae
Leiostyla anglica (Wood, 1828)
Lauria cylindracea (Da Costa, 1778)

fam. Walloniidae
Acanthinula aculeata (Müller, 1774)
Spermodea lamellata (Jeffreys, 1830)
Plagyrona placida (Shuttleworth, 1852)

fam. Punctidae
Punctum pygmaeum (Draparnaud, 1801)

fam. Zonitidae
Vitrea crystallina (Müller, 1774)
Aegopinella nitidula (Draparnaud, 1801)
Oxychilus cellarius (Müller, 1774)

fam. Limacidae
Deroceras agreste (Linne, 1758)

fam. Euconulidae
Euconulus fulvus (Müller, 1774)

fam. Clausiliidae
Clausilia bidentata rugosa (Draparnaud, 1801)
Balea perversa (Linne, 1758)

fam. Testacellidae
Testacella maugei Ferussac, 1819

fam. Helicidae
Oestophora barbula (Rossmassler, 1838)
Oestophora lusitanica (Pfeiffer, 1848)
Caepaea nemoralis (Linne, 1758)

3. Discussion: The land snails fauna of seems be less varied than expected, an aspect probably related with the absence of calcareous rocks and soils in the area.

The species found are mainly woodland snails that need a wet rainy climate and a rich and shadowy wood with a thick leaf-mould.

Helicids are poor in diversity and number. Only *Oestophora lusitanica* and *Caepaea nemoralis* are fairly commons. Otherwise, *Leiostyla anglica*, *Acanthinula aculeata* and *Clausilia rugosa* are the most abundant and widespread species.

Spermodea lamellata and *Plagyrona placida*, already signalized by SILVA e CASTRO (1887), (GITTENBERGER, 1989), seems to be rare and restricted to a few isolated parts.

Columella aspera (fig. 1) is another common species that lives under mosses and dead leaves. This reference to Buçaco is interesting because, at the moment, only *Columella edentula* (Draparnaud, 1805) is cited to Portugal. NOBRE (1941), refers that “*Vertigo edentula* (Draparnaud)” is only rarely found in Alfena, Trava-gem e Ermesinde, situated in Northern Portugal. However, his description and fig-uration are quite similar to that of *C. aspera*, presented in KERNEY & CAMERON (1979): “(1) shell with 5-6 whorls, about one less than in *C. edentula*; (2) whorls more convex and suture more deep; (3) growth-ridges very regular and well marked”. So, we think that the “*Vertigo edentula*” of Nobre is, in fact, a *C. aspera*. Consequently, the existence of *C. edentula* in Portugal needs confirmation. Both species, with distribution areas commonly confounded (KERNEY & CAMERON, 1979), might coexist, but the single presence of a few isolated populations of *C. aspera* in the North and Central Portugal is more likely.

Fig. 1 — *Columella aspera* Waldén, 1966 — Buçaco, Portugal (x12).

RESUMO

A Mata do Buçaco é um arboreto rico em espécies exóticas, as quais todavia, coexistem com uma flora autóctone residual. Estas características, conjuntamente com o clima moderado, mas húmido, do local, aparentam fornecer condições óptimas para a existência de moluscos terrestres.

Destes, a fauna encontrada compreende 21 espécies, das quais as mais abundantes são *Leiostryla anglica*, *Acanthinula aculeata* e *Clausilia bidentata rugosa*. Pelo contrário, é notória a pobreza em Helicóides. *Columella aspera* Waldén, 1966 é citada como nova para Portugal e comparada com *C. edentula*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the help of Carla Bernardo with the grammar revision.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALLORGE, V. (1974) — La Bryoflore de la forêt du Buçaco (Portugal).— *Rev. Bryol. Lichén.*, **40** (4): 304-452.
- DA SILVA e CASTRO, J. (1887) — Contributions à la faune malacologique du Portugal, II-IV.— *Jorn. Sci. Math. Phys. Nat.*, **11** (44): 232-249.
- FIGUEIREDO, J.M. (1930) — Subsídios para o estudo da flora lenhosa e herbácea da Mata do Buçaco.— *Bol. Minist. Afric.*, **12** (1-6): 21-56.
- FRANCO, J.A. (1951) — Notas sobre a flora lenhosa da Mata do Buçaco.— *Bol. Soc. Brot.*, sér. 2, **25**: 197-248.
- GITTENGERGER, E. (1989) — Additional data concerning the systematics and the remarkable ranges of three species of landsnails, known from Sintra.— *Publ. Ocas. Soc. Port. Malac.*, **13**: 13-16.
- GIUSTI, F.; CASTAGNOLO, L. & MANGANELLI, G. (1985) — La fauna malacologica delle faggete italiane: brevi cenni di ecologia, elenco delle specie e chiavi per il riconoscimento dei generi e delle entità più comuni.— *Boll. Malac., Publ. Soc. Ital. Malac.*, **21** (5-6): 69-144.
- HENRIQUES, J. (1885) — A vegetação espontânea do Buçaco.— *Bol. Soc. Brot.*, **3**: 109-123.
- KERNEY, M.P. & CAMERON, R.A.D. (1979) — *A field guide to the land snails of Britain and North-west Europe*. W. Collins Sons & Co Ltd, London, 290 p.
- NOBRE, A. (1941) — *Fauna malacológica de Portugal*.— II — *Moluscos terrestres e fluviais*.— *Mem. Est. Mus. Zool. Univ. Coimbra*, **124**: 1-279.
- PAIVA, J.A.R. (1987) — A Mata do Buçaco.— *Bol. Aderav, Inst. Bot. Univ. Coimbra*, **16**: 1-21.
- PALAZZI, S. (1988) — On some landsnails collected in Sintra.— *Publ. Ocas. Soc. Port. Malac.*, **10**: 17-18.
- SEABRA, A.F. (1905) — A regeneração da fauna ornithológica do Buçaco.— *Bol. Dir. Geral Agric.*, **8** (2): 1-160.